

Reproducibility Study of The Unfairness of Popularity Bias in Music Recommendation: A Reproducibility Study

Experiment Design, Assignment 2: Group 21

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Abstract

In this Reproducibility Study of the paper “The Unfairness of Popularity Bias in Music Recommendation: A Reproducibility Study”, we tried to reproduce the results found by Kowald D., Schedl M., Lex E. We did this during a course of our Data Science Master Curriculum at TU Vienna, called Experiment Design for Data Science VU 188.992. In this second project of the course, we were tasked with the analysis of several papers from conferences in the field of Information Retrieval. This is the report of our work.

Paper Selection

The first paper we looked at is called “Conformative Filtering for Implicit Feedback Data” [1]. It deals with recommender systems and their performance regarding unconsumed items. It is stated that there can be numerous individual reasons for non-consumption, like lack of resources, which leads to the wrong assumptions of no interest. However, these exceptions fade regarding a large group of people who share the same interests. To test this, multidimensional clustering is performed on the implicit feedback data. We liked this paper because it examines a very hands-on issue with a real-world dataset. The code is available at a GitHub repository and it is based mostly on Java. It is well-documented with detailed steps on how to run the code.

Next, we analysed the paper “The Unfairness of Popularity Bias in Music Recommendation: A Reproducibility Study” [2]. This is a reproducibility study of another paper, which analysed recommender systems based on movie recommendations and found that the results are better when users are interested in popular items. This means that users interested in unpopular items get worse recommendations. This paper reproduces the results based on music recommendations. The code is available on GitHub and uses Python in a Jupyter notebook. We were interested in this paper as it focuses on a widely used topic and fortified the findings of the first paper that people not interested in the mainstream get significantly worse recommendations.

The third paper selected is “Generating High-Quality Query Suggestion Candidates for Task-Based Search” [3]. It states that currently the query suggestions are mainly based on a major search engine. Three different approaches are presented as alternatives. These approaches consist of a popular suffix model, a neural language model and a sequence-to-sequence model. The code is available on a GitHub repository and exclusively written in Python. The documentation of it is quite brief. It can be executed with a single line and one parameter. We preselected this paper as it challenges the suggestions of the dominant use of a major search engine. However, we found that the code provided is quite brief and would not pose a great challenge to run and analyse.

We selected the second paper. While all three topics and domain areas were interesting to us, the code complexity and degree of documentation varied a lot. We did not want to choose a paper with a low potential of encountering reproducibility challenges or finding improvements.

Experiment Setup

As discussed in the section above, the selected paper we reproduced was “The Unfairness of Popularity Bias in Music Recommendation: A Reproducibility Study” [2]. As the name already suggests, it is itself a reproduction study, building upon a different paper called “The unfairness of popularity bias in recommendation” [4]. While the original paper uses movie data, the reproduction attempts to prove the same points with a different dataset and examines, if the results also hold true in the music domain. Both papers explore the popularity bias which occurs in recommender systems.

Popularity bias occurs when recommender algorithms do not treat all items equally fair. Less popular items are therefore underrepresented in recommendations. Both papers examine the popularity bias from a user perspective and conclude that algorithms not only underrepresent unpopular items, but also deliver worse recommendations for people who like less popular

items (Claim A). Additionally, the recommendations based on these unpopular items are worse for the users (now depending on the popularity of the items in certain user profiles, these users accordingly get recommendations of differing quality). Furthermore, the authors demonstrate that a substantial number of users is not or to a lesser degree interested in popular artists. (Claim B)

The process of proving these results is carried out by experimenting on the respective dataset. For this implementation of the experiment, we will focus on the reproducibility study with the dataset in the music domain. Notably, the data used for proving the statements in the music domain is by far larger than the data used in the original paper. The LFM-1b dataset [5] consists of about 1 billion listening events of 120.000 users. For the experiment, the authors took a subset of 3.000 users, who represent three user groups (low, medium, and high mainstream) and their respective events. The mainstreamness score used in this process is defined in the original paper. The code of some preprocessing during this extraction is also given in Python scripts (others/Track_Dist.py, others/Matrix_Gen.py) The resulting subset is available at zenodo [6]. It now contains 1,755,361 user-artist interactions between 3,000 users and 352,805 music artists. In comparison, the original paper uses a movie dataset with only 3.900 items.

Now, the paper's code and its characteristics are discussed in more detail. The authors analyse the data with a Python notebook. They used a Python 3 version that is not specified more concretely, as well as an unspecified Jupyter version. Additionally, some standard Python packages are used (Pandas, Matplotlib, NumPy, SciPy, Sklearn), but also the recommendation algorithms from the open-source Surprise Toolkit for the rating predictions. For the execution of the code for the experiment, the following parameters were used: `<item_threshold>` filters according to the count of a user-artist interaction (no filtering was used here). `<my_seed>` sets a seed for usages of the Python library "random", NumPy, and the train-test split (here the seed was 0).

At first some analysis of the used data was carried out: Distributions of the number of artists per user, number of artists overall and listening counts per artist. The top artists were selected from the latter, then the authors showed the distribution of the percentages of popular artists in user profiles. The conclusion from the listening counts per artist is, "that only a few artists are listened to by many users, while most artists (i.e., the long-tail) are only listened to by a few users." Concerning the distribution of the percentages of popular artists in user profiles, the authors showed that the low-mainstream user group (1000 of the 3000 users) has 20% or more unpopular artists in their profiles (with unpopular artists being those that are not in the top 20% of artists). This proves Claim B of the authors. The authors then investigated the correlation between profile size and average popularity of the artists in user profiles. It turns out, "users with a smaller profile size tend to listen to more popular artists".

The execution of the music recommendation is done with a 80/20 train-test split and uses state-of-the-art algorithms: Baseline

(Random, MostPopular, and UserItemAvg), KNN-based (UserKNN and UserKNNAvg) and Non-Negative Matrix Factorization (NMF). Proving the popularity bias, in all algorithms except Random, popular items are recommended more often than unpopular items (in NMF there is only a slight bias).

For the investigation concerning the user groups, the authors use the Group Average Popularity (GAP) metric from the original paper. They compare the popularity of recommendations a user group receives with the popularity of artists in their user profiles. The results from the original paper (user groups show a difference in GAP difference) are not clearly reproduced, since the algorithms do not show a clear difference between the user groups (except for MostPopular, where this is inherent to the specification of the algorithm). The authors think this is due to the different sizes of the dataset (352,805 artists compared to 3,900 movies). Random and NMF provide the recommendations with the least increase in popularity.

Finally, the authors look at the Mean Average Error (MAE). According to this, NMF delivers the best recommendations in all user groups, however with all algorithms the low mainstream users receive the worst recommendations and the medium mainstream users the best (probably due to the medium mainstream group having the biggest average profile size). Therefore, they prove the popularity bias for users, since low mainstream users receive the worst results. This proves Claim A.

Our Reproduction

In order to reproduce the results from the paper, we followed the setup provided and made assumptions whenever we had to deviate from it if not enough information was available. From the beginning we decided to test the entire experiment on three separate computers with different operating systems, specifically we ran the experiments on Windows 10, macOS 10.15.7 and Linux Mint 19.3.

To start, we fetched the data from Zenodo [6] where we downloaded the three datasets "low_main_users.txt", "medium_main_users.txt" and "high_main_users.txt" which are subsets from the LFM-1b dataset. Next, we cloned the repository [7] and opened the main notebook using Jupyter 5.7.7 and running Python 3.7.6. When executing the notebook, we used the same parameters as the paper, mentioned in the previous section (seed=0, item_threshold=1).

The code did not execute successfully. In order to resolve this issue, an index drop was necessary (`df_events = df_events.reset_index(level=0)`) after which the experiment ran through. However, we discovered several instances of deprecated code warnings which could be traced back to the use of the comparison operator "is not" which was subsequently replaced with "!=". Overall, results we computed were nearly identical to the ones from the original paper summarized in claim A, claim B and the performance of the GAP metric: While our reproduced experiment proved both claims A and B semantically, we focused on a comparison on the most granular level which are the metrics provided in the paper: UserItemAvg, UserKNN, UserKNNAvg and NMF for the three user categories low mainstreamness

(LowMS), medium mainstreamness (MedMS) and high mainstreamness (HighMS). Our results showed a near identical performance to the original paper only deviating less than 0.1% of the original numbers (see table Table 2). As the original paper does not provide the exact numbers for each of the 3,000 artists' recommendations, but rather the aggregated values we did not see great value in statistically testing the few metrics provided and therefore concentrated on the absolute deviations from these metrics. Still, we set out to further investigate the factors and components that might influence our results. To see our results in comparison with the results of the original paper, go to the "Result Tables" section at the end of this document.

One factor that prevented a fully transparent analysis of the code was the absence of a clear description of the dataset subsampling process. While the paper semantically describes how the 3,000 users were selected ("Our subset consists of the 1,000 users with lowest mainstreamness scores [...], the 1,000 users with a mainstreamness score around the median [...], and the 1,000 users with the highest mainstreamness scores [...]") the necessary code to reproduce this sub-sampling process is not provided which is why this data component could not be analysed completely.

Another factor that hindered a transparent reproduction and comparison of the results were missing sub-results: Although the notebook is structured in several intermediary steps with multiple sub-results printed out, there is no reference in the paper of how these sub-results should look like in a successful run - they are only shown in graphical plots. Relevant sub-results include the distributions of the number of artists per user and the listening counts per artist.

To further experiment with the code, we decided to run it while adjusting the seed parameter as well as the item_threshold parameter. When changing the seed from 0 to 50 (and 25 respectively), the resulting metrics changed only slightly, reaching a difference of up to 0.3% compared to the original paper's results. When changing the item_threshold from 1 to 2, the results differed from the original paper by up to 40%. Overall, apart from the different operating systems on different computers, the (sub-)dataset which could not be reproduced properly without instructions, the main components to experiment with were the parameters seed and item_threshold. The former one might be an interesting candidate to follow up as this might be the source for the deviating results in the experiment: the magnitude of the differences matches, leading to the assumption that the seed generation in Python might have changed between the original release of the paper and the execution of these experiments.

To sum up, while the reproduction of the results of the experiment included some issues and challenges, we managed to reproduce the final numbers down to a variation of 0.1% which might be traced back to a different seed that was used in the original experiments.

Analysis & Conclusion

At first, we will evaluate the paper and the provided code. We found that the paper itself is well-written. It can be easily understood, it is well-structured, and the concepts applied are clear. The code in the Jupyter notebook follows good coding standards. It is well readable, so that a third party can easily understand what it is doing. Moreover, it is structured in many separate blocks which further improves its readability. On top, comments - usually at the start of a block - help describing the code even more although the last third of the code would benefit from more descriptions. All in all, the reproduction of the movielens experiments worked out well. The paper tested and analysed the findings of the original paper in a completely different domain. We tested and analysed the experiment setup within the domain and the exact same data. Apart from the initial errors which could have been resolved during the execution it was well runnable.

The documentation of the code was rather compact and short. Hence, we recommend improving in this area: More detailed instructions on how to get the code running might prevent some of the code errors as well as open the experiment up to a wider field of users which might not have as much programming experience as the authors of the paper. In a first step this could include a step-by-step guide on how a setup should be done and where to download the packages and libraries needed such as Jupyter or surprise. Also, the only version number provided was „Python 3“. Precise version numbers of the included external packages and libraries would further improve the reproducibility potential of the experiment as this would easily eliminate another possible source of errors. As most blocks produced outputs in a form of a system print-out or a plot, it would be helpful to include the results of these outputs to be able to compare the results more granularly. Furthermore, the code or exact process of the subsampling of the dataset should be included to enable third parties to also reproduce this step and achieve a higher level of transparency and traceability. Finally, a disclaimer indicating that many external components such as libraries or programming languages might change over time as a result of updated versions would further help to raise the awareness of potential sources of error.

Last but not least, standardisation is an essential element to ensure reproducibility. At this point we would like to emphasize that the authors made good use of standard libraries and frameworks as part of their programming pipeline. Widely used tools such as Jupyter, pandas and NumPy were used. Also, the use of the package surprise is well justified for it is popular and implemented by many projects in similar areas. In general, with external libraries dependencies are created.

To summarise, the paper was rather well reproducible. After some corrections, the code ran through in our tests as well and produced not identical, but very close numbers. As the documentation was scarce, this forms our main basis of recommendation: including more information would enable a higher probability of a seamless reproduction of the experiment.

Result Tables*Table 1: Original Results from Paper*

User group	UserItemAvg	UserKNN	UserKNNAvg	NMF
LowMS	42.991	49.813	46.631	38.515
MedMS	33.934	42.527	37.623	30.555
HighMS	40.727	46.036	43.284	37.305
All	38.599	45.678	41.927	34.895

Table 2: Our Results: Seed 0, item_threshold 1

User group	UserItemAvg	UserKNN	UserKNNAvg	NMF
LowMS	42.948	49.760	46.581	38.422
MedMS	33.900	42.484	37.585	30.596
HighMS	40.686	45.991	43.242	37.285
All	38.5612	45.6321	41.8842	34.8799

Table 3: Our Results: Seed 50, item_threshold 1

User group	UserItemAvg	UserKNN	UserKNNAvg	NMF
LowMS	42.739	49.189	46.322	38.108
MedMS	34.257	42.993	38.063	31.000
HighMS	40.509	45.888	43.030	37.090
All	38.5893	45.6459	41.9388	34.8914

Table 4: Our Results: Seed 0, item_threshold 2

User group	UserItemAvg	UserKNN	UserKNNAvg	NMF
LowMS	54.808	62.758	59.528	51.218
MedMS	47.057	57.305	51.587	43.858
HighMS	55.723	62.264	59.115	52.796
All	51.9985	60.4374	56.2414	48.7644

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